

Accuracy Analysis of a Commercial Photovoltaic Production Forecasting Solution in Norway

SINTEF Notat

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SINTEF Academic Press

SINTEF Notes 53

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Keywords: Photovoltaic system, forecasting, accuracy assessment

Cover photo: © BERRE / SINTEF

ISSN 1894-2466

ISBN 978-82-536-1877-7 (pdf)

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Foreword

The purpose of this technical report is to provide detailed analyses of the accuracy performance of a commercial photovoltaic (PV) production forecasting solution implemented for a building in Oslo, Norway. These analyses are based on forecasting and monitoring data collected from January 2025 to June 2025.

This technical report provides an example of a detailed PV forecasting algorithm accuracy test. It can serve as a foundation for other similar studies on forecasting accuracy.

Oslo, Norway, 15-07-2025

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Summary

This technical report provides detailed analyses of the accuracy performance of a commercial photovoltaic production forecasting solution implemented for a building in Oslo, Norway. These analyses are based on forecasting and monitoring data collected from January 2025 to June 2025. The evaluation shows that the normalized mean absolute error (NMAE) is 3.5% on average for PV power forecasts and 2% for energy forecasts. Power forecasting errors range from 1.5% in winter to 5% in summer, increasing slightly with the forecasting horizon. Energy forecasting errors benefit from temporal aggregation, which smooths short-term inaccuracies, thus decreasing the summed energy forecasting error with increasing prediction horizon. The forecasting service tends to slightly underestimate production during high-output periods and overestimate during low-output periods. While absolute errors remain moderate, normalized metrics can appear inflated during low-production periods. Four service outages occurred during the evaluation period, resulting in 4% missing data and no automated fault alerts. Future studies are recommended to compare this commercial solution with simple data-driven models using the same inputs to better understand the sources of forecasting error.

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1. Case Description

1.1. PV Installation

The photovoltaic (PV) panels of the investigated installation are located on the roof and facades of a 10 000 m² building located in Oslo, Norway. The building is newly built (2021) with a primary energy demand of 49 kWh/year per m² (usable floor area). As a comparison, the primary energy demand of similar buildings in Oslo built after 2010 ranges from 50 to 100 kWh/year per m² (see Annex A). The current building case can thus be considered to be energy efficient.

The total installed PV capacity is 337 kWp, consisting of a mix of Building-Attached PV (BAPV) and Building-Integrated PV (BIPV):

- 2 East-West-oriented BAPV systems on the roofs
- 1 South-oriented BAPV system on the façade
- 1 South-oriented BIPV system on the face
- 1 West-oriented BIPV system on the façade

The BIPV modules are both green-coloured and black. The design of the PV modules' layout is defined by their location and orientation in relation to the sky, the orientation of the building's longest facades, and the regulations regarding the aesthetics of the PV façade.

The design PV production is 224 000 kWh/year. In 2024 (a normal year in terms of sunshine in Oslo), the PV production was 215 032 kWh, which is close to the design production. The peak production was 209 kWp.

1.2. Forecasting Model

The PV production forecasting model tested in this report is a commercial solution based on a physics-informed machine learning-driven algorithm that provides PV production forecasting each hour with a forecasting horizon of 48 hours.

This forecasting model is optimized for trading electricity, meaning that it is best suited to predict the spot PV production at a given time step in the future.

The model is recalibrated/adjusted around 4 times a day with new data received and the actual PV production monitored at the PV installation site. The forecasting model accounts for the predicted solar irradiance and outdoor temperature at the location of the PV installation. This weather forecast is provided by an external weather forecasting provider. The uncertainty on the irradiance forecasting will thus impact the PV production forecasting as well.

2. Accuracy Assessment Methodology

To assess the accuracy of a forecasting model for PV production, if there is no significant outliers in the forecast, it is commonly recommended to use MAE (Mean Absolute Error), MSE (Mean Square Error), and their associated relative (normalized) metrics Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and related Coefficient of the Variation of the Root Mean Square Error (CVRMSE). It is also recommended to normalize the MAE by the peak installed PV power (in *kWp*).

These standard accuracy metrics are computed on point-to-point forecasting (i.e., comparing each forecasting point at different forecasting horizon – 1h, 6h, 12h, 24h, 48h – with its corresponding actual production data point for the same date and time) at all time (over the entire considered period of time, e.g., an entire month, including nighttime, which will tend to give better results because accounting for night time periods when the forecasting is perfect, i.e., no production) and only during PV production time (when the actual PV production of electricity is not 0). In addition, these metrics are also computed on the cumulative PV production forecast and actual production over a given period: the next 1 hour, 6 hours, 12 hours, 24 hours and 48 hours. This also accounts for nighttime with no production, and might introduce some compensation effects (over-estimations and under-estimations compensating each other within the considered time period), which could lead to more favorable accuracy than the point-to-point accuracy analyses. For point-to-point accuracy metrics that are normalized by the value of the real PV production, the metrics are not defined when the real PV production is 0 (division by 0). For those instances, the value of the metrics is set as NaN, which is then ignored when computing the mean and percentiles of those metrics.

The following accuracy metrics are used for this analysis and defined here after [1][2]. The equation notation conventions are detailed here below:

- x : True/reference PV production data point.
- y : Predicted/forecasted PV production data point.
- \bar{x}, \bar{y} : Mean value of the whole dataset or sub-dataset.
- n : Number of data points in the whole dataset or sub-dataset.

2.1. MAE

The Mean Absolute Error (MAE) or mean absolute difference is computed as:

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - x_i|}{n}$$

2.2. MAPE

The Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) or mean absolute percentage difference is computed as:

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i - x_i}{x_i} \right| \times 100 \quad [\%]$$

2.3. NMAE

The Normalized Mean Absolute Error (NMAE) or normalized mean absolute difference is computed as the MAE normalized by the installed peak PV power production (337 kWp). NMAE could be computed with other normalization factors, such as the average PV

production over a given period or the maximum recorded peak power production. However, in the case of PV installation, normalization by the installed peak PV power is more common:

$$NMAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - x_i|}{n \times 337 \text{ kWp}} \times 100 \text{ [\%]}$$

For the summed PV energy production, the NMAE is calculated with the installed peak PV power production times the prediction/aggregation horizon as the normalization factor:

$$NMAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - x_i|}{n \times 337 \text{ kWp} \times \Delta t} \times 100 \text{ [\%]}$$

2.4. MSE

The Mean Square Error (MSE) or mean square different is computed as:

$$MSE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - x_i)^2}{n}$$

2.5. RMSE

The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) or root mean square different is computed as:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{MSE} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - x_i)^2}{n}}$$

2.6. CVRMSE

The Coefficient of the Variation of the Root Mean Square Error (CVRMSE) is computed as the RMSE normalized by the average of the reference PV production:

$$CVRMSE = \frac{1}{\bar{x}} \cdot RMSE \times 100 = \frac{1}{\bar{x}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - x_i)^2}{n}} \times 100 \text{ [\%]}$$

2.7. NRMSE

The Normalized Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE) is computed as the RMSE normalized by the installed peak PV power production (337 kWp):

$$NRMSE = \sqrt{MSE} \times \frac{1}{337 \text{ kWp}} \times 100 = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - x_i)^2}{n}} \times \frac{1}{337 \text{ kWp}} \times 100 \text{ [\%]}$$

For the summed PV energy production, the NRMSE is calculated with the installed peak PV power production times the prediction/aggregation horizon as the normalization factor:

$$NRMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - x_i)^2}{n}} \times \frac{1}{337 \text{ kWp} \times \Delta t} \times 100 \text{ [\%]}$$

3. Results

The forecasting PV production data (continuously streamed via a dedicated API to the forecasting service) is compared to the actual PV production recorded at the building case (downloaded via Energinet.net) for the months of January, April, and June 2025, and the entire first half of the year 2025 (beginning of January to end of June 2025).

After realignment of the data timestamp and data treatment, point-to-point and summed PV production forecasts are analyzed over a period of time and prediction horizons of 1h, 6h, 12h, 24h, and 48h.

3.1. January 2025

The time series figures of PV production below present a qualitative comparison of the forecasting model accuracy for different aggregation periods and forecasting horizons in January 2025.

Figure 1. Time series comparison of real and forecasted PV production in January 2025 for different forecasting horizons.

Figure 2. Close-up on the forecasting under-estimation during a high-production day and the forecasting over-estimation during a low-production day in January 2025 for different forecasting horizons.

Figure 3. Point-to-point comparison of real and forecasted PV production in January 2025 for different forecasting horizons.

One can observe in Figure 1, Figure 2, and Figure 3 that the forecasting tends to under-estimate PV production on high-production days and over-estimate PV production on low-production days during winter in January 2025.

Figure 4. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 1 hour in January 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 1 hour.

Figure 5. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 6 hours in January 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 6 hours.

Figure 6. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 12 hours in January 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 12 hours.

Figure 7. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 24 hours in January 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 24 hours.

Figure 8. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 48 hours in January 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 48 hours.

Figure 9. Point-to-point comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over different horizons in January 2025.

Similarly to the hourly point forecasting, one can observe in Figure 4, Figure 5, Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8, and Figure 9 that the forecasting tends to under-estimate summed PV production on high-production days and over-estimate summed PV production on low-production days during winter in January 2025.

3.2. April 2025

The time series figures of PV production below present a qualitative comparison of the forecasting model accuracy for different aggregation periods and forecasting horizons in April 2025.

Figure 10. Time series comparison of real and forecasted PV production in April 2025 for different forecasting horizons.

Figure 11. Close-up on the forecasting under-estimation during a high-production day and the forecasting over-estimation during a low-production day in April 2025 for different forecasting horizons.

Figure 12. Point-to-point comparison of real and forecasted PV production in April 2025 for different forecasting horizons.

Similarly to January, one can observe in Figure 10, Figure 11, and Figure 12 that the forecasting tends to slightly under-estimate PV production on high-production days and slightly over-estimate PV production on low-production days during spring in April 2025.

Figure 13. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 1 hour in April 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 1 hour.

Figure 14. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 6 hours in April 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 6 hours.

Figure 15. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 12 hours in April 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 12 hours.

Figure 16. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 24 hours in April 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 24 hours.

Figure 17. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 48 hours in April 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 48 hours.

Figure 18. Point-to-point comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over different horizons in April 2025.

Similarly to the hourly point forecasting, one can observe in Figure 13, Figure 14, Figure 15, Figure 16, Figure 17, and Figure 18 that the forecasting tends to slightly under-estimate summed PV production on high-production days and slightly over-estimate summed PV production on low-production days during spring in April 2025.

Overall, the forecasting for April 2025 is better than for January 2025, when the PV production is very low.

3.3. June 2025

The time series figures of PV production below present a qualitative comparison of the forecasting model accuracy for different aggregation periods and forecasting horizons in June 2025.

Figure 19. Time series comparison of real and forecasted PV production in June 2025 for different forecasting horizons.

Figure 20. Close-up on the forecasting during a high- and low-production days in June 2025 for different forecasting horizons.

Figure 21. Point-to-point comparison of real and forecasted PV production in June 2025 for different forecasting horizons.

Similarly to April, one can observe in Figure 19 **Error! Reference source not found.**, Figure 20, and Figure 21 that the forecasting tends to slightly under-estimate PV production on high-production days and slightly over-estimate PV production on low-production days during summer in June 2025.

Figure 22. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 1 hour in June 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 1 hour.

Figure 23. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 6 hours in June 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 6 hours.

Figure 24. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 12 hours in June 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 12 hours.

Figure 25. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 24 hours in June 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 24 hours.

Figure 26. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 48 hours in June 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 48 hours.

Figure 27. Point-to-point comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over different horizons in June 2025.

Similarly to the hourly point forecasting, one can observe in Figure 22, Figure 23, Figure 24, Figure 25, Figure 26, and Figure 27 that the forecasting tends to slightly underestimate summed PV production on high-production days and slightly over-estimate summed PV production on low-production days during summer in June 2025.

Overall, the forecasting for June 2025 is good, because the PV production is quite high, except, of course, when there is a prolonged loss of forecasting service data stream.

3.4. January to June 2025

The time series figures of PV production below present a qualitative comparison of the forecasting model accuracy for different aggregation periods and forecasting horizons from January to June 2025.

Figure 28. Time series comparison of real and forecasted PV production from January to June 2025 for different forecasting horizons.

Figure 29. Point-to-point comparison of real and forecasted PV production from January to June 2025 for different forecasting horizons.

One can observe in Figure 28 **Error! Reference source not found.** and Figure 29 **Error! Reference source not found.** that the forecasting tends to slightly under-estimate PV production on high-production days and slightly over-estimate PV production on low-production days.

Figure 30. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 1 hour from January to June 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 1 hour.

Figure 31. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 6 hours from January to June 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 6 hours.

Figure 32. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 12 hours from January to June 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 12 hours.

Figure 33. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 24 hours from January to June 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 24 hours.

Figure 34. Comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over 48 hours from January to June 2025 for a forecasting horizon of 48 hours.

Figure 35. Point-to-point comparison of real and forecasted summed PV production over different horizons from January to June 2025.

Similarly to the hourly point forecasting, one can observe in Figure 30 **Error! Reference source not found.**, Figure 31 **Error! Reference source not found.**, Figure 32 **Error! Reference source not found.**, Figure 33 **Error! Reference source not found.**, Figure 34 **Error! Reference source not found.**, and Figure 35 **Error! Reference source not found.** that the forecasting tends to slightly under-estimate summed PV production on high-production days and slightly over-estimate summed PV production on low-production days.

Table 1 below summarizes the different accuracy and error performance metrics computed for the different evaluation periods and the different forecasting horizons.

One can observe that the magnitude of the error metric can vary significantly between the different performance metrics. However, the recommended performance metric is the Normalized Mean Absolute Error (NMAE) with the installed peak power as the normalization factor (here 337 kWp for the normalization of the PV power supply, and $337 \text{ kWp} \times \text{prediction/aggregation horizon}$ for the summed PV production). Moreover, one can also see that the evaluation period has a large influence: including the nighttime period in the accuracy assessment of the point-to-point PV power forecasting introduces a bias that reduces the error. Indeed, during nighttime, there is no PV production, and the hourly forecasting is perfect at 0 kW. Nevertheless, this is not representative of the accuracy of a PV production forecasting model. It is thus chosen to exclude the nighttime from the accuracy assessment and only consider data during daytime (i.e., with PV production above 0 kW).

The discussion section of this report thus focuses solely on the point-to-point production time only (daytime) PV power NMAE, and the total PV energy production over a given horizon period NMAE.

Table 1. Accuracy / error metrics assessing the performance of the forecasting service against the real on-site PV production.

Aggregation	Forecasting horizon	Accuracy / error metric	Unit	January 2025			April 2025			June 2025			January-June 2025		
				Mean	10th percentile	90th percentile	Mean	10th percentile	90th percentile	Mean	10th percentile	90th percentile	Mean	10th percentile	90th percentile
Point-to-point all time	1 hour	MAE	kW	1,6	0,0	6,1	8,3	0,0	22,4	14,2	0,0	36,7	7,0	0,0	19,9
	6 hours	MAE	kW	1,6	0,0	6,3	8,4	0,0	23,1	14,5	0,0	38,5	7,2	0,0	20,6
	12 hours	MAE	kW	1,6	0,0	6,2	8,8	0,0	23,7	14,5	0,0	37,8	7,3	0,0	20,8
	24 hours	MAE	kW	1,7	0,0	6,6	9,4	0,0	24,9	15,0	0,0	38,8	7,8	0,0	22,9
	48 hours	MAE	kW	1,8	0,0	6,6	10,3	0,0	29,5	17,1	0,0	47,7	8,8	0,0	25,7
Point-to-point production time only (daytime)	1 hour	MAE	kW	4,6	0,1	11,9	10,8	0,2	27,8	14,9	0,6	37,0	10,8	0,2	26,7
	6 hours	MAE	kW	4,7	0,1	12,6	11,0	0,2	28,0	15,1	0,6	38,7	11,2	0,3	27,4
	12 hours	MAE	kW	4,7	0,1	12,6	11,6	0,2	28,4	15,2	0,6	38,3	11,2	0,3	26,8
	24 hours	MAE	kW	5,0	0,1	13,2	12,2	0,2	29,2	15,9	0,6	38,9	12,1	0,3	28,1
	48 hours	MAE	kW	5,2	0,1	12,9	13,8	0,3	32,7	18,8	0,8	47,7	13,9	0,2	31,6
Total energy production over horizon period	1 hour	MAE	kWh	1,6	0,0	6,1	8,6	0,0	24,1	25,4	0,0	80,4	9,3	0,0	23,2
	6 hours	MAE	kWh	8,4	0,0	27,2	38,8	0,1	104,4	133,9	1,4	408,6	46,1	0,0	101,1
	12 hours	MAE	kWh	16,4	0,1	40,4	71,1	7,0	165,3	255,1	12,9	898,1	87,0	1,0	165,3
	24 hours	MAE	kWh	30,4	7,3	62,5	133,6	20,5	236,2	489,0	29,3	1684,9	164,0	15,0	247,6
	48 hours	MAE	kWh	49,4	14,0	90,3	249,2	60,4	506,4	969,7	47,7	3381,9	304,2	27,8	525,8
Point-to-point all time	1 hour	MAPE	%	68 %	0 %	100 %	41 %	0 %	100 %	70 %	0 %	113 %	59 %	0 %	100 %
	6 hours	MAPE	%	69 %	0 %	100 %	41 %	0 %	100 %	72 %	0 %	107 %	61 %	0 %	100 %
	12 hours	MAPE	%	69 %	0 %	100 %	43 %	0 %	100 %	75 %	0 %	115 %	63 %	0 %	100 %
	24 hours	MAPE	%	74 %	0 %	100 %	44 %	0 %	100 %	80 %	0 %	111 %	67 %	0 %	100 %
	48 hours	MAPE	%	84 %	0 %	127 %	51 %	0 %	100 %	95 %	0 %	162 %	77 %	0 %	110 %

Table 1. Continuation.

Point-to-point production time only (daytime)	1 hour	MAPE	%	199 %	19 %	638 %	60 %	3 %	101 %	88 %	4 %	127 %	100 %	4 %	149 %
	6 hours	MAPE	%	199 %	18 %	484 %	61 %	3 %	112 %	89 %	4 %	124 %	104 %	4 %	158 %
	12 hours	MAPE	%	201 %	18 %	604 %	65 %	3 %	100 %	93 %	3 %	137 %	108 %	5 %	163 %
	24 hours	MAPE	%	216 %	18 %	511 %	66 %	4 %	122 %	99 %	3 %	151 %	114 %	5 %	168 %
	48 hours	MAPE	%	245 %	17 %	617 %	76 %	5 %	154 %	118 %	4 %	181 %	131 %	6 %	203 %
Total energy production over horizon period	1 hour	MAPE	%	199 %	19 %	638 %	61 %	3 %	101 %	90 %	5 %	112 %	100 %	5 %	142 %
	6 hours	MAPE	%	179 %	21 %	306 %	67 %	3 %	100 %	84 %	4 %	100 %	100 %	4 %	122 %
	12 hours	MAPE	%	180 %	19 %	551 %	445 %	2 %	89 %	892 %	3 %	100 %	286 %	3 %	127 %
	24 hours	MAPE	%	164 %	14 %	661 %	208 %	2 %	50 %	227 %	2 %	100 %	122 %	2 %	122 %
	48 hours	MAPE	%	90 %	12 %	193 %	22 %	3 %	55 %	40 %	2 %	100 %	42 %	3 %	100 %
Point-to-point all time	1 hour	NMAE	%	0,5 %	0,0 %	1,8 %	2,5 %	0,0 %	6,7 %	4,2 %	0,0 %	10,9 %	2,1 %	0,0 %	5,9 %
	6 hours	NMAE	%	0,5 %	0,0 %	1,9 %	2,5 %	0,0 %	6,9 %	4,3 %	0,0 %	11,4 %	2,1 %	0,0 %	6,1 %
	12 hours	NMAE	%	0,5 %	0,0 %	1,8 %	2,6 %	0,0 %	7,0 %	4,3 %	0,0 %	11,2 %	2,2 %	0,0 %	6,2 %
	24 hours	NMAE	%	0,5 %	0,0 %	2,0 %	2,8 %	0,0 %	7,4 %	4,5 %	0,0 %	11,5 %	2,3 %	0,0 %	6,8 %
	48 hours	NMAE	%	0,5 %	0,0 %	2,0 %	3,0 %	0,0 %	8,8 %	5,1 %	0,0 %	14,2 %	2,6 %	0,0 %	7,6 %
Point-to-point production time only (daytime)	1 hour	NMAE	%	1,4 %	0,0 %	3,5 %	3,2 %	0,1 %	8,2 %	4,4 %	0,2 %	11,0 %	3,2 %	0,1 %	7,9 %
	6 hours	NMAE	%	1,4 %	0,0 %	3,7 %	3,3 %	0,1 %	8,3 %	4,5 %	0,2 %	11,5 %	3,3 %	0,1 %	8,1 %
	12 hours	NMAE	%	1,4 %	0,0 %	3,7 %	3,4 %	0,1 %	8,4 %	4,5 %	0,2 %	11,4 %	3,3 %	0,1 %	7,9 %
	24 hours	NMAE	%	1,5 %	0,0 %	3,9 %	3,6 %	0,1 %	8,7 %	4,7 %	0,2 %	11,6 %	3,6 %	0,1 %	8,5 %
	48 hours	NMAE	%	1,5 %	0,0 %	3,8 %	4,1 %	0,1 %	9,7 %	5,6 %	0,2 %	14,2 %	4,1 %	0,1 %	9,4 %
Total energy production over horizon period	1 hour	NMAE	%	0,5 %	0,0 %	1,8 %	2,5 %	0,0 %	7,2 %	7,5 %	0,0 %	23,9 %	2,8 %	0,0 %	6,9 %
	6 hours	NMAE	%	0,4 %	0,0 %	1,3 %	1,9 %	0,0 %	5,2 %	6,6 %	0,1 %	20,2 %	2,3 %	0,0 %	5,0 %
	12 hours	NMAE	%	0,4 %	0,0 %	1,0 %	1,8 %	0,2 %	4,1 %	6,3 %	0,3 %	22,2 %	2,2 %	0,0 %	4,1 %
	24 hours	NMAE	%	0,4 %	0,1 %	0,8 %	1,7 %	0,3 %	2,9 %	6,0 %	0,4 %	20,8 %	2,0 %	0,2 %	3,1 %
	48 hours	NMAE	%	0,3 %	0,1 %	0,6 %	1,5 %	0,4 %	3,1 %	6,0 %	0,3 %	20,9 %	1,9 %	0,2 %	3,3 %

Table 1. Continuation.

Point-to-point all time	1 hour	MSE	16	0	38	312	0	504	742	0	1345	264	0	398
	6 hours	MSE	17	0	40	298	0	536	755	0	1482	268	0	424
	12 hours	MSE	17	0	38	329	0	563	793	0	1430	275	0	432
	24 hours	MSE	19	0	44	399	0	618	801	0	1506	305	0	524
	48 hours	MSE	20	0	44	422	0	872	930	0	2275	346	0	662
Point-to-point production time only (daytime)	1 hour	MSE	49	0	141	302	0	773	511	0	1368	283	0	711
	6 hours	MSE	50	0	160	306	0	785	526	0	1500	295	0	751
	12 hours	MSE	50	0	159	336	0	807	549	0	1470	301	0	717
	24 hours	MSE	56	0	174	381	0	852	581	0	1516	346	0	812
	48 hours	MSE	60	0	167	459	0	1070	820	1	2275	447	0	1000
Total energy production over horizon period	1 hour	MSE	16	0	38	345	0	582	2466	0	6471	583	0	540
	6 hours	MSE	300	0	740	6198	0	10894	72339	2	166938	15380	0	10224
	12 hours	MSE	695	0	1632	15907	49	27312	223613	166	806874	45503	1	27335
	24 hours	MSE	1459	54	3901	44020	419	55779	654636	859	2838931	129141	224	61315
	48 hours	MSE	3245	197	8158	131262	3643	256448	2,E+06	2278	1,E+07	450453	773	276432
Point-to-point all time	1 hour	RMSE	4	0	6	18	0	22	27	0	37	16	0	20
	6 hours	RMSE	4	0	6	17	0	23	27	0	39	16	0	21
	12 hours	RMSE	4	0	6	18	0	24	28	0	38	17	0	21
	24 hours	RMSE	4	0	7	20	0	25	28	0	39	17	0	23
	48 hours	RMSE	4	0	7	21	0	30	30	0	48	19	0	26
Point-to-point production time only (daytime)	1 hour	RMSE	7	0	12	17	0	28	23	1	37	17	0	27
	6 hours	RMSE	7	0	13	17	0	28	23	1	39	17	0	27
	12 hours	RMSE	7	0	13	18	0	28	23	1	38	17	0	27
	24 hours	RMSE	7	0	13	20	0	29	24	1	39	19	0	29
	48 hours	RMSE	8	0	13	21	0	33	29	1	48	21	0	32
Total energy production over horizon period	1 hour	RMSE	4	0	6	19	0	24	50	0	80	24	0	23
	6 hours	RMSE	17	0	27	79	0	104	269	1	409	124	0	101
	12 hours	RMSE	26	0	40	126	7	165	473	13	898	213	1	165
	24 hours	RMSE	38	7	62	210	20	236	809	29	1685	359	15	248
	48 hours	RMSE	57	14	90	362	60	506	1560	48	3382	671	28	526

Table 1. Continuation.

Point-to-point all time	1 hour	CVRMSE	%	159 %	0 %	241 %	49 %	0 %	62 %	53 %	0 %	71 %	54 %	0 %	66 %
	6 hours	CVRMSE	%	162 %	0 %	249 %	48 %	0 %	64 %	53 %	0 %	74 %	54 %	0 %	69 %
	12 hours	CVRMSE	%	161 %	0 %	243 %	50 %	0 %	66 %	54 %	0 %	73 %	55 %	0 %	69 %
	24 hours	CVRMSE	%	171 %	0 %	260 %	55 %	0 %	69 %	55 %	0 %	75 %	58 %	0 %	76 %
	48 hours	CVRMSE	%	176 %	0 %	261 %	57 %	0 %	82 %	59 %	0 %	92 %	62 %	0 %	86 %
Point-to-point production time only (daytime)	1 hour	CVRMSE	%	92 %	1 %	156 %	31 %	0 %	49 %	34 %	1 %	55 %	32 %	0 %	51 %
	6 hours	CVRMSE	%	93 %	1 %	166 %	31 %	0 %	50 %	34 %	1 %	58 %	33 %	0 %	53 %
	12 hours	CVRMSE	%	93 %	1 %	166 %	33 %	0 %	51 %	35 %	1 %	57 %	33 %	0 %	52 %
	24 hours	CVRMSE	%	98 %	1 %	173 %	35 %	0 %	52 %	36 %	1 %	58 %	36 %	1 %	55 %
	48 hours	CVRMSE	%	101 %	1 %	170 %	38 %	1 %	58 %	43 %	1 %	71 %	41 %	0 %	61 %
Total energy production over horizon period	1 hour	CVRMSE	%	159 %	0 %	240 %	51 %	0 %	67 %	96 %	0 %	155 %	80 %	0 %	77 %
	6 hours	CVRMSE	%	113 %	0 %	178 %	36 %	0 %	48 %	86 %	0 %	131 %	69 %	0 %	56 %
	12 hours	CVRMSE	%	86 %	0 %	132 %	29 %	2 %	38 %	77 %	2 %	145 %	59 %	0 %	46 %
	24 hours	CVRMSE	%	63 %	12 %	103 %	25 %	2 %	28 %	67 %	2 %	139 %	50 %	2 %	35 %
	48 hours	CVRMSE	%	48 %	12 %	75 %	22 %	4 %	30 %	66 %	2 %	142 %	47 %	2 %	37 %
Point-to-point all time	1 hour	NRMSE	%	1,2 %	0,0 %	1,8 %	5,2 %	0,0 %	6,7 %	8,1 %	0,0 %	10,9 %	4,8 %	0,0 %	5,9 %
	6 hours	NRMSE	%	1,2 %	0,0 %	1,9 %	5,1 %	0,0 %	6,9 %	8,2 %	0,0 %	11,4 %	4,9 %	0,0 %	6,1 %
	12 hours	NRMSE	%	1,2 %	0,0 %	1,8 %	5,4 %	0,0 %	7,0 %	8,4 %	0,0 %	11,2 %	4,9 %	0,0 %	6,2 %
	24 hours	NRMSE	%	1,3 %	0,0 %	2,0 %	5,9 %	0,0 %	7,4 %	8,4 %	0,0 %	11,5 %	5,2 %	0,0 %	6,8 %
	48 hours	NRMSE	%	1,3 %	0,0 %	2,0 %	6,1 %	0,0 %	8,8 %	9,0 %	0,0 %	14,2 %	5,5 %	0,0 %	7,6 %
Point-to-point production time only (daytime)	1 hour	NRMSE	%	2,1 %	0,0 %	3,5 %	5,2 %	0,1 %	8,2 %	6,7 %	0,2 %	11,0 %	5,0 %	0,1 %	7,9 %
	6 hours	NRMSE	%	2,1 %	0,0 %	3,7 %	5,2 %	0,1 %	8,3 %	6,8 %	0,2 %	11,5 %	5,1 %	0,1 %	8,1 %
	12 hours	NRMSE	%	2,1 %	0,0 %	3,7 %	5,4 %	0,1 %	8,4 %	7,0 %	0,2 %	11,4 %	5,1 %	0,1 %	7,9 %
	24 hours	NRMSE	%	2,2 %	0,0 %	3,9 %	5,8 %	0,1 %	8,7 %	7,2 %	0,2 %	11,6 %	5,5 %	0,1 %	8,5 %
	48 hours	NRMSE	%	2,3 %	0,0 %	3,8 %	6,4 %	0,1 %	9,7 %	8,5 %	0,2 %	14,2 %	6,3 %	0,1 %	9,4 %
Total energy production over horizon period	1 hour	NRMSE	%	1,2 %	0,0 %	1,8 %	5,5 %	0,0 %	7,2 %	14,7 %	0,0 %	23,9 %	7,2 %	0,0 %	6,9 %
	6 hours	NRMSE	%	0,9 %	0,0 %	1,3 %	3,9 %	0,0 %	5,2 %	13,3 %	0,1 %	20,2 %	6,1 %	0,0 %	5,0 %
	12 hours	NRMSE	%	0,7 %	0,0 %	1,0 %	3,1 %	0,2 %	4,1 %	11,7 %	0,3 %	22,2 %	5,3 %	0,0 %	4,1 %
	24 hours	NRMSE	%	0,5 %	0,1 %	0,8 %	2,6 %	0,3 %	2,9 %	10,0 %	0,4 %	20,8 %	4,4 %	0,2 %	3,1 %
	48 hours	NRMSE	%	0,4 %	0,1 %	0,6 %	2,2 %	0,4 %	3,1 %	9,6 %	0,3 %	20,9 %	4,1 %	0,2 %	3,3 %

4. Discussion and Conclusion

Focusing on the NMAE (the recommended accuracy metric), one can observe in Figure 36 that the normalized error for the PV power supply forecasting is around 3.5%: ranging from 1.5% for low-production periods (winter) to 5% for high-production periods (summer). The error for low-production periods is lower because the normalization factor is the same as that of the high-period (the installed peak power production), and the MAE is one order of magnitude higher in high-production periods compared to low-production ones. Moreover, one can see that the forecasting error increases slightly with the forecasting horizon: from 3.2% to 4.1% over the entire evaluation period.

Figure 36. NMAE of the daytime PV power supply forecasting as a function of forecasting horizon, and for different periods.

As shown in Figure 37, the NMAE of the summed PV energy supply forecasting is around 2%, ranging from 0.5% to 7%. Similarly to the PV power supply forecasting, the error for low-production periods is one order of magnitude lower than that of the high-production periods. In addition, the error of the PV energy supply forecasting tends to decrease with the forecasting horizon because summing up/integrating the energy production over a longer time tends to cancel out small under-estimations and over-estimations (compensation effect).

Figure 37. NMAE of the daytime summer PV energy supply forecasting as a function of forecasting horizon, and for different periods.

Overall, the commercial PV production forecasting service performs fairly well. However, it tends to slightly underestimate PV production on high-production days and slightly overestimate it on low-production days. Some of the normalized error metrics (e.g., MAPE and CVRMSE) can show very large values in winter when production is very small compared to the total installed capacity. Because of the normalization used in those metrics, any small forecasting errors during low-production periods result in poor relative accuracy, even though the absolute error remains moderate compared to the system's installed capacity. Therefore, it is more appropriate to evaluate forecast performance over longer periods (more than 3 months) when PV production is substantial.

Regarding service reliability (the stability of data updates and streaming via a dedicated API), there were four service outages between January and June 2025. One outage was caused by an issue in the data stream of the real monitored PV production from the building study case. The data stream was restored after contacting the service provider. There was no automated fault detection or service downtime alert. The missing data from the PV forecasting service accounts for about 4% of the total monitoring data points.

Future studies on this PV system case could compare the commercial forecasting solution with simple data-driven models (e.g., ARX models) fed with the same weather forecast and monitored PV production inputs. Replacing the forecasted weather data with actual recordings could help determine the error caused by the weather forecast and the model itself.

References

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Annex A

Figure A1. Primary energy demand of school buildings in Oslo as a function of their year of construction. The red data point is the current study case building.

Accuracy Analysis of a Commercial Photovoltaic Production Forecasting Solution in Norway

This report presents a detailed analysis of the accuracy performance of a commercial photovoltaic production forecasting solution implemented for a school building in Oslo, Norway. The analyses are based on forecasting and monitoring data collected from January 2025 to June 2025.

The report provides an example of detailed photovoltaic production forecasting algorithm accuracy testing. It can serve as a foundation for other similar studies on forecasting accuracy.